

RESEARCH ON FACTORS INFLUENCING THE INTENT TO USE NETFLIX MOVIES IN VIETNAM

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Abstract

The Netflix movies market is steadily growing, especially during the complex COVID-19 pandemic. Consumers, instead of opting for free movie streaming services with potential risks and copyright violations, are choosing to pay for a better experience while emphasizing responsibility for protecting copyrights and supporting authors and producers. This research aims to examine the factors influencing the intent to use Netflix movie streaming services among surveyed individuals, primarily focusing on employees aged 18 to 22 in Vietnam. Participants were surveyed through online and offline questionnaires. The author conducted logistic regression analysis, treating the use of Netflix movies as the dependent variable, with five independent variables sourced from a literature review. Through online and offline survey questionnaires and multivariate regression models, the study identified and concluded the factors influencing employees' intent to use Netflix movie streaming services in Vietnam. Data were quantitatively analyzed using IBM SPSS 20.0. The research results identified five positively influencing factors on the intent to use Netflix movie streaming services: Price perception, Risk perception, Attitude, Ethical awareness, Subjective norms. Among these factors, Price perception had the strongest influence on the intent to use Netflix movies, while the Subjective norms factor was found to be insignificant. Consequently, the article suggests managerial implications for businesses to attract customers and promote the Netflix movies market.

Keywords: Intent to Use, Online Movie Streaming, Netflix Movies, Payment for Netflix Movies.

1. INTRODUCTION

In modern life, the standard of living continues to improve, leading to an increasing demand for entertainment. Entertainment has become an essential need for people, serving to satisfy physical, intellectual, and artistic needs. It is not only an individual's need but also a communal one. People can choose any form of activity or service for entertainment, and one of the most popular choices is movie streaming services (in theaters or online). This is considered a prevalent form of entertainment among today's youth and is expected to continue to thrive in the future (Lan, 2021).

However, life undergoes unexpected changes that cannot be predicted. For example, the world, and specifically Vietnam, faced the acute respiratory illness caused by the novel Coronavirus

(COVID-19), disrupting people's lives and habits. Daily routines and basic needs have been significantly altered (Moon, 2020). Non-essential businesses like bars, pubs, cinemas, etc., were required to close (Tinh, 2020). With the COVID-19 situation still complex, the government has urged people to limit unnecessary movements and avoid large gatherings to prevent disease spread. Even daily grocery shopping has been restricted due to the increasing complexity of the pandemic. As a result, consumers have spent more time at home, shifting their activities like exercise, shopping, learning, and entertainment to the online environment. Recent market research by various companies has shown that COVID-19 has had a strong impact on the consumer behavior of Vietnamese people (Huy & Nhi, 2021).

According to Saigon Giai Phong newspaper's statistics, at the onset of the COVID-19 pandemic (around early 2020), the number of people going to cinemas for entertainment decreased by 30 to 40%. Even after the social distancing measures were lifted, allowing businesses to reopen, the number of moviegoers continued to drop significantly, with a 50-70% decrease in attendance and a 70% reduction in revenue. It is clear that consumers are still cautious about the pandemic and prefer staying home for entertainment rather than taking risks (Lan, 2020).

Specifically, online entertainment platforms such as YouTube's Multi-Channel Networks (MCN) in Vietnam, such as MeTub and POPS, have experienced significant growth since the beginning of the pandemic. With POPS entertainment channels, the viewership has grown by 22% compared to the same period last year, with consistent viewership on both weekdays and weekends. Livestream viewership on POPS has surged by up to 300%, featuring entertainment content for children, artist interaction livestreams, and pandemic-related news. In addition to entertainment, educational programs and skill-building content for children have also seen substantial growth. Online movie streaming services at home, such as Galaxy Play, FPT Play, Netflix, etc., have also attracted viewers with a wide range of genres, including feature films, TV series, documentaries, and scientific content (Trang, 2020).

The reality shows that online movie platforms are becoming increasingly popular, especially during social distancing measures. With more time spent at home, consumers, especially young individuals, such as students and employees, have shown a strong preference for these services, with statistics indicating up to 97% (Lan, 2020). Among various forms of online entertainment, movies and TV series have the highest viewership. Online television is evidently a growing trend as cinemas remain closed (Lan, 2021).

Websites providing online movie streaming services are continuously evolving, regularly updating their content to attract consumers (Vũ, 2020). Websites offering free movie streaming services like bilutvs.net, phimmoizz.net, fullphim.net, etc., provide a wide range of movie genres. However, alongside these options come potential risks such as exposure to negative ads or inadvertently clicking on malicious links that can infect personal devices with viruses. Paid movie streaming platforms are also thriving, with examples like FPT Play, Galaxy Play, VieON, etc. These platforms offer licensed movies, excellent quality, and reasonable fees, making them a popular choice among consumers. Instead of choosing free streaming sites that violate copyrights, have poor video quality, low audio quality, negative content in ads, or pirated movies, consumers are making intelligent choices by opting to pay for a better experience.

According to statistics from VTV, nearly 60% of users subscribe to paid online streaming services, which is a promising signal. Netflix movies platforms now possess a vast amount of data on viewers' habits and preferences. Based on this data, online movie libraries can suggest content to customers (Khôi, 2020). Moreover, the cost of a paid online streaming subscription is only about one-third to half the cost of a movie ticket (Ayanbadejo et al., 2020). Blockbuster films and exclusive content will be released on online platforms simultaneously or shortly after their theatrical release (Anh, 2021; Nam, 2021). This trend excites consumers, and they are gradually shifting towards watching more Netflix movies, changing their consumer behavior even after the pandemic has subsided and is under control. However, as demand continues to rise, so do opportunities and challenges. Netflix movie service providers need to reevaluate their current situation to address issues and approach customers more effectively, reducing barriers to encourage customer subscriptions.

2. THEORETICAL BACKGROUND

2.1 Service

Today, services encompass a wide range of activities and exchanges in various fields and at different levels. Researchers and experts have not yet provided a unified definition of services due to their complexity, intangibility, and diversity.

Some definitions of services offered by experts are as follows:

According to Philip Kotler (1987): "Services are any activities or benefits that one party can offer to another. In which a specific provider must be intangible and does not lead to any ownership rights. The production of services may or may not be associated with any tangible product."

The 2013 Law defines services as "intangible commodities, which are not separated during production and consumption, including types of services within the system of Vietnam's product industries as regulated by law."

In general, services can be considered as an economic activity with a social aspect, and service products do not involve the transfer of ownership rights. They exist in an intangible form and aim to address human needs promptly while potentially adding value to other economic activities.

2.2 Entertainment Services

Entertainment services involve providing individuals with aesthetically pleasing activities during leisure time, aiming to relieve mental stress, create interest, and contribute to the holistic development of individuals in terms of intelligence, physical well-being, and aesthetics. Entertainment activities are part of human activities, including labor production, personal relationships in society, material life, and spiritual life. Services fall into the fourth category and are the only activities not linked to any specific need (Wikipedia, 2020).

In the common sense of the term, the primary purpose of the verb "entertain" is to provide the public with something interesting or enjoyable, capturing their attention during a specific

period when the audience perceives it. Many things can capture our attention, including emotions such as pain, fear, joy, or admiration for a magnificent scene in a movie, all of which fall under the category of entertainment (Lewis, 1978).

Driven by the human need for entertainment, providers of entertainment services have emerged over time.

One of the forms of entertainment services for consumers is online streaming platforms. With these platforms, all that's needed is an internet connection to access a vast library of movies spanning various genres, from romance and action to comedy, documentaries, science fiction, and more. Some popular online streaming platforms include HBO, K+, Netflix, and Film+. The consumers of this service are referred to as viewers or audiences. While the movies themselves are physical products, the act of watching them evokes emotions and is considered an entertainment activity. This leads to the emergence of providers of online streaming services.

2.3 Online Streaming

Online streaming is a new-generation television format with programs and on-demand channels delivered over high-speed internet connections. Internet television is also known as Internet Protocol television (IPTV). Originating from Europe, it was provided by reputable companies in France (France Telecom), Italy (Fastweb), the UK (Homechoice), and many other countries. BT Group, a leading fixed-line telephone service provider in the UK, is currently negotiating with content providers to launch its own service. Unlike cable and satellite TV, which transmit all channels simultaneously, internet television delivers a separate video channel depending on the subscriber's request. The larger the fixed-line phone network, the greater the access to customers. Currently, internet TV has come to Vietnam with the name Internet TV, and it has undergone some changes. That is, you use which service package, there will be preferred channels - the default of the service provider, not the subscriber's choice. Service providers like VTVnet, VTCnet, and FPT group preferred channels to create different service packages with prices that match users' capabilities and desires. One of the advantages of internet television over cable TV is that it is not limited to broadcast times. Audiences won't miss their favorite programs. They can watch them at any time because television programs are digitized and stored as program files with audio and images on the server. Viewers only need to click on the program file on the service provider's website to watch the program they want (Nam, 2014).

2.4. Subscription Model

Freemium is a combination of the words "free" and "premium." It's a unique business model related to providing customers with both free and premium services. Companies offer initial basic services for free to all users as a trial while providing premium services or additional features.

The idea of the Freemium business model was formulated around March 2006 by Fred Wilson. During this period, profits from advertising on websites had significantly decreased, and Freemium was used as a reliable alternative solution.

In the Freemium model, a business offers free services to consumers initially as a way to establish a foundation for future transactions. By providing basic features of software, games, or services for free, companies build relationships with customers, eventually offering them advanced services, additional utilities, removal of storage or usage limitations, enhanced user experiences, or ad removal for a fee (Wikipedia, 2021).

2.5 Ethical Awareness

Ethical awareness is a crucial first step in the process of making ethical decisions and is defined as the "ability of an individual to recognize that a situation has ethical implications" (Rest, 1986). It pertains to being aware of the different choices of action that can occur and understanding how each action will impact others (Bebeau et al., 1999). When researchers delved deeper into Rest's definition, they found various interpretations and explanations of ethical awareness (Jordan, 2007). This study focuses on ethical awareness as the ability to recognize ethical issues in a situation. Scholars have recognized the importance of ethical awareness, stating that "if one does not recognize the ethical dimension of a situation, one cannot address any ethical issue" (Clarkeburn, 2002). If an individual is unaware that a situation has ethical relevance, they will not consider ethical concerns when making decisions and will instead decide based on other data, such as economic rationality (Jones, 1991). Therefore, exploring ethical awareness along with ethical judgment in the process of ethical decision-making is valuable (Jordan, 2007).

2.6. Intention to Use

Intention refers to the factor used to assess an individual's capability to perform a specific behavior. According to Ajzen (1991), intention is motivational and reflects an individual's willingness to engage in a specific behavior. The intention to use mobile applications is the likelihood that users will use applications on their mobile devices regularly and consistently in the future (Webster et al., 1993; Venkatesh et al., 2000).

Following the definitions provided by Webster et al., 1993, and Venkatesh et al., 2000, in this study, the author discusses the intention to use a form of entertainment service on an online platform. Therefore, the intention to use by consumers in the future is likely to involve users using online entertainment services regularly and consistently.

2.7. Theory of Consumer Behavior

As life continues to evolve, human needs also develop continuously, leading to changes in human behavior over time. Many researchers and experts have provided definitions of consumer behavior, which can be understood through some representative definitions:

According to the American Marketing Association, consumer behavior is "the dynamic interaction of affect and cognition, behavior, and the environment by which human beings conduct the exchange aspects of their lives." In simpler terms, consumer behavior includes the thoughts and perceptions individuals have and the actions they take during consumption. Factors such as word-of-mouth, advertising, price information, packaging, product appearance, and more can influence consumers' perceptions, thoughts, and behaviors.

Or, according to Kotler & Levy, consumer behavior is the specific actions of an individual when making purchase, usage, and disposal decisions regarding products or services.

Bennet (1988) defines consumer shopping behavior as "the actions that consumers exhibit in seeking, purchasing, using, evaluating, and disposing of products and services that they expect will satisfy their needs."

Kotler (2001) emphasizes the importance of understanding consumer needs, preferences, and behaviors through consumer behavior research. He states that for marketers, it's crucial to understand what consumers think, feel, and do while also providing clear value to all target customers to build effective marketing strategies. Therefore, according to Kotler, marketers must have a deep understanding of consumer needs and analyze the factors that have influenced consumer shopping behavior.

2.8. Related Theoretical Models

Theory of Reasoned Action (TRA)

The TRA model, also known as the Theory of Reasoned Action, predicts the intention to purchase (Ajzen & Fishbein, 1975) and includes two main factors: Attitude toward the behavior and Subjective Norms influencing Intention to perform the behavior, leading to the final behavior.

However, Ajzen & Fishbein (1975) acknowledged a limitation in the TRA model, assuming that behavior is decided based on the intention to perform that behavior. Therefore, this theory is only applicable to behaviors with pre-existing intentions.

When consumers form the intention to purchase, they are free to act, but in reality, actions are influenced greatly by external factors. The TRA allows for predicting and explaining trends in behavior by focusing on consumers' attitudes toward the behavior itself rather than the specific product or service of the business (Mitra Karami, 2006).

Theory of Planned Behavior (TPB)

According to Ajzen (1991), this concept is inherited and developed from the Theory of Reasoned Action (TRA) by Ajzen & Fishbein, 1975. The TPB model was created to overcome the limitation of the previous theory, which assumed that human behavior is controlled by rationality. It is considered an improved model compared to TRA. Perceived behavioral control is expressed through the ease or difficulty of performing a specific behavior or whether there are any restrictions when performing that behavior (Ajzen, 1991).

Theory of Perceived Risk (TPR)

The Theory of Perceived Risk (TPR) by Bauer (1960) includes two main aspects: Perceived Risk with Product/Service (PRP) and Perceived Risk in the Context of Online Transaction (PRT). PRP relates to the potential financial loss, time consumption, loss of functionality, opportunities, or product/service-related risks. PRT, on the other hand, pertains to risks associated with conducting e-commerce transactions through electronic devices, such as safety and confidentiality.

2.9. Relevant Studies

Factors Driving and Hindering the Purchase Intention of Online Music Streaming Services – Teresa Fernandes and João Guerra (2019)

Universal access rights to online content, non-ownership transfer, and the revolutionizing of consumer behavior. The music industry serves as an example: the sales of physical products have decreased significantly, and even online music stores are increasingly threatened by the rise of on-demand online music streaming services (MSS). However, MSS faces difficulties in convincing users to choose the premium (paid) version. Therefore, the purpose of this study is to assess what drives (inhibits) the purchase intention of MSS by users and to examine the role of gender and age. Based on data collected from 318 MSS users, the study shows that both perceived value and perceived cost are important predictors of the intention to purchase MSS, with the negative impact of past intention outweighing the positive impact, while the moderating effects of age and gender are supported. Our research contributes to a deeper understanding of MSS purchase intention and provides valuable insights for MSS providers.

Image 1: Model of factors promoting and inhibiting the intention to purchase online music streaming services – Teresa Fernandes and João Guerra (2019)

Source: Teresa Fernandes and João Guerra, 2019

Where:

Perceived Usefulness – PU

Perceived Enjoyment – PE

Perceived Value – PV

Perceived Fee – PF

The hypotheses presented are as follows:

H1: Technical competence is negatively related to PU in the context of MSS (online movie streaming services).

H2: Technical competence is negatively related to PE in the context of MSS.

H3: PU is positively related to PV in the context of MSS.

H4: PE is positively related to PV in the context of MSS.

H5: PV is positively related to the intention to purchase in the context of MSS.

H6: PF is negatively related to the intention to purchase in the context of MSS.

H7: Intention to purchase significantly varies by gender in the context of MSS.

H8: Intention to purchase significantly varies by age in the context of MSS.

This study, conducted by Domenico Sardanelli, Agostino Vollero, Alfonso Siano & Gianmaria Bottoni in 2019, examines the factors influencing consumers' intentions to pay for online movie streaming services. The introduction of various online movie streaming services has raised new questions about how online consumers deal with both legal and illegal options to access content. Starting with the theory of planned behavior as a foundation, the authors expanded existing models in the literature by incorporating specific factors related to consumer behavior in this particular domain. A quantitative survey was conducted in the Italian market, and structural equation modeling was employed to analyze the data. Attitude, involvement in the product, moral judgment, and past behavior frequency were identified as the most significant factors in explaining the intention to pay for online movie streaming services. The paper provides detailed insights for policymakers and industry managers regarding necessary marketing communication strategies to minimize the risk of digital copyright violations.

The author has presented hypotheses for the research model as follows:

- H1: Intention to pay for online movie streaming services is influenced by attitude toward this purchasing behavior.
- H2: Involvement in movies positively affects the intention to pay for online movie streaming services.
- H3: Attitude mediates the impact of involvement on the intention to pay for online movie streaming services.
- H4: Moral judgment regarding the purchase of illegal movies affects the intention to pay for online movie streaming services.
- H5: Subjective norms related to the purchase of illegal movies lead to the intention to pay for online movie streaming services.
- H6: Ethical judgments mediate the influence of subjective norms related to the purchase of illegal movies on the intention to pay for online movie streaming services.
- H7: Intention to pay for online movie streaming services is influenced by the frequency of past online media product purchases.
- H8: Intention to pay for online movie streaming services is negatively affected by perceived risk when shopping online.
- H9: Frequency of past media product purchases negatively affects perceived risk when shopping online.

These hypotheses are part of the research model based on the Theory of Planned Behavior (TPB) that examines the factors influencing consumers' intentions to pay for online movie streaming services.

3. HYPOTHESES AND RESEARCH MODEL

3.1 Attitude

According to Ajzen's Theory of Reasoned Action (TRA) (1967), attitude is one of the crucial factors that determine behavioral intentions. It refers to how an individual perceives a specific behavior. These attitudes are influenced by two factors: the belief in the outcomes of the behavior and the evaluation of the potential outcomes. When customers use online services, their attitudes are shaped by their evaluations during the usage process, considering aspects like professionalism, security, consumer rights, convenience, and the compatibility between the cost and the online service provided by the business. Consumer attitudes in e-commerce and technology are assessed to have a positive impact on their intentions and usage behaviors. Therefore, the research hypothesis is proposed:

Hypothesis H1: Attitude positively affects the intention to use Netflix movie services among employees in Vietnam.

3.2 Subjective Norms

Based on research by Taylor and Told (1995), this pressure comes from the supportive or non-supportive attitudes of family, friends, and other significant individuals toward performing a certain behavior. Ajzen (1991) further developed his definition of subjective norms, indicating that individuals intend to perform a behavior after considering the influence of significant others on themselves and perceiving that many others also perform the same intended behavior. Previous studies have shown a positive correlation between subjective norms and behavioral intentions. In this research, the author addresses the influence of family, friends, and important individuals on an individual's intention to perform a behavior. Additionally, there is an impact from government policies and media propaganda. The support or opposition of these entities significantly affects an individual's intention to perform a behavior. Therefore, it can be understood that just one opposition or agreement, whether negative or positive, can influence the individual's thinking and potentially change their behavior. Based on this, the research hypothesis is proposed:

Hypothesis H2: Subjective norms positively affect the intention to use Netflix movie services among employees in Vietnam.

3.3 Perceived Risk

In the theory of perceived risk (TPR), perceived risk includes risk perception related to products/services and risk perception related to online transactions. Risks when using online services may include personal information exposure, device contamination with malware, virus infection, exposure to negative content in advertisements, etc. Bhatnagar et al. (2000) suggest that the trend of online shopping will decrease as perceived risk increases. According to Wu, Vassileva, and Zhao (2017), the lack of security and information confidentiality is a significant factor inhibiting the intention to use online services on the Internet. Along with the benefits that bring satisfaction to customers, there are potential risks mentioned above that make customers apprehensive about paid online movie streaming services. Users may lose data, their personal devices may be infected with viruses, or, worse, their personal information may be lost and used for other purposes beyond their control. Based on these considerations, the research hypothesis is proposed:

Hypothesis H3: Perceived risk negatively affects the intention to use Netflix movie services among employees in Vietnam.

3.4 Price Perception

Price perception involves comparing objective prices with subjective prices, which is the customer's perception of the price of a product or service (Jacoby and Olson, 1977). Research shows that customers are not always satisfied with the price levels set by product or service providers. Therefore, high satisfaction with the price, along with the product or service provided by the supplier, positively influences the usage behavior of consumers. The author assumes that this also applies to Netflix movie services. Therefore, the research hypothesis is proposed:

Hypothesis H4: Price perception positively affects the intention to use Netflix movie services among employees in Vietnam.

3.5 Ethical Perception

Ethical perception is an individual's ability to recognize a situation related to ethical issues (Rest, 1986). Previous studies on digital copyright infringement (Sardanelli et al., 2019) have also indicated that ethical identity, as well as a high perception of digital copyright infringement, plays a significant role in increasing the trend of purchasing mainstream, legal, and copyrighted media products. Purchasing itself can be considered an ethical behavior. Therefore, ethical perception can play an essential role in persuading consumers to reject illegal, non-copyrighted channels. Based on consumers' perceptions of refraining from copyright infringement, it can increase the likelihood of consumers paying for online movie streaming services. Therefore, the research hypothesis is proposed:

Hypothesis H5: Ethical perception positively affects the intention to use Netflix movie services among employees in Vietnam.

3.6 Research Model

The author's model inherits from the TRA, TPB, and TPR models. However, the consideration of not fully applying the TAM model is due to the following reasons: The author observes that intentions to use Netflix movie services primarily lean towards subjective norms and attitudes (perceptions) of individuals. This means that considering the behavioral intention is sufficient. Moreover, the level of technology usage in this research is not high, as simple online operations and applications are involved. Additionally, the author referred mainly to the study "Research Model of the TPB on Factors Influencing the Intention to Pay for Online Movie Streaming Services" by Sardanelli et al. (2019), which makes it appropriate to refer to, inherit, and develop Sardanelli et al.'s model into this research.

4. RESEARCH METHOD

This research was conducted by surveying 200 customers to collect survey data through online and offline survey questionnaires (direct surveys). The collected information was used to evaluate the reliability and validity of the measurement scale, verify the scale, and assess the model's suitability. The collected data will be processed using SPSS 20.0 software. After encoding and cleaning the data, the following steps will be taken to assess the reliability of the measurements using Cronbach's Alpha coefficient, and exploratory factor analysis (EFA) will be performed to examine the convergence and discriminant validity of the component variables.

4.1 Sampling Method

The population of the study includes all male and female employees aged 18 to 22 years who are currently studying in Vietnam. According to Hair et al. (2010), in factor analysis, the minimum number of observations should be 4 or 5 times the number of observed variables. This study involves factor analysis, and there are 29 observed variables in the research model;

hence, a minimum sample size of $n = 29 \times 5 = 145$ is required. In this study, the author chose a sample size of 200 in the official study, which is considered large enough to meet the conditions.

4.2 Research Measurement Scale

Table 1: Research Measurement Scale

Factor	Observed Variables	Source
Attitude	Using the Netflix Movies service makes me feel delighted. I find it easy to use with the monthly payment method. The functionalities in the Netflix Movies platform interface are user-friendly. The Netflix Movies platform interface is appealing to me. The service provider offers all the movies I want to watch.	Shin & Kim (2008), Oliveira & colleagues (2016)
Subjective Norm	I care because people around me use it. Messages in the media about protecting copyright affect me. Decisions about using my service can be influenced by advice on social media. Family and friends support my use of the Netflix Movies service. I use the Netflix Movies service because of my personal needs, not due to social pressure.	Lu & colleagues (2005), Hà (2020)
Perceived Risk	My personal information will be securely protected. I do not face the risk of data loss. I believe the service is stable, with a high-speed internet connection and clear audio-visual quality. I will not encounter issues related to the spread of malware or viruses to my personal devices. I perceive Netflix Movies service as safe.	Wu, Vassilevaa & Zhaob (2017) Lan (2015)
Perceived Price	The subscription prices for the movie packages are reasonable for me. Any additional costs incurred when I subscribe to the movie packages are not significant. The monthly cost I pay to watch movies is reasonable for me. The movie packages and promotional programs are attractive to me. The price of the movie packages is important to me.	Shin & Kim (2008) Oliveira & colleagues (2016)
Ethical Perception	I feel ashamed in front of others and society when I watch "pirated" movies without copyrights. Respecting copyrights by paying for the movie packages makes me feel proud. Watching unauthorized movies causes harm to the author and producers, and violating movie copyrights is unfair to the authors. I will recommend everyone to use Netflix movies services to protect intellectual property rights of the authors.	Sardanelli, D., Vollero, A., Siano, A., & Bottoni, G. (2019)
Intention to Use	I intend to use Netflix movies services in the future. I am willing to share my positive experiences with those around me. I plan to recommend Netflix movies services to my family, friends, and important people in my life. Netflix movies services should be encouraged for use.	Oliveira & colleagues (2016) Chi (2014)

4.3. Data Collection

Through both online and offline surveys, the author collected 200 responses and obtained 175 valid responses (accounting for 87.5%) to be used as research data. According to the data table, females constitute a higher proportion than males, and the majority are second-year employees. Monthly income is mainly below 3 million VND, and 87.5% of customers are aware of or interested in Netflix movie services.

5. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

5.1. Results of the Reliability Analysis of the Scale

The results in Table 2 show that all scales have Cronbach's Alpha reliability coefficients greater than 0.6. The intercorrelation coefficients of the observed variables are all greater than 0.3. Therefore, all 25 observed variables in the component scale and 4 observed variables in the intention to use scale are reliable. The results of the exploratory factor analysis for the independent variables (Table 2) show that 5 factors are extracted, and all 29 observed variables have factor loadings greater than the permissible standard (Factor Loading > 0.5). At the same time, the Bartlett's test shows that there is a significant correlation among the variables in the population (significance level sig = 0.000 < 0.05) with a Kaiser-Meyer-Olkin (KMO) measure of 0.894 (0.5 < KMO < 1). The total extracted variance is 73.729, which means it explains 73.729% of the data's variability.

Table 2: Cronbach's Alpha Test Results

Scale Component	Initial Number of Observed Variables	Cronbach's Alpha Coefficient	Total Variable Correlation Coefficient
Attitude	5	0.882	≥ 0.719
Subjective Norm	5	0.892	≥ 0.736
Risk Perception	5	0.937	≥ 0.833
Price Perception	5	0.905	≥ 0.765
Ethical Perception	5	0.906	≥ 0.769
Intention to Use	4	0.881	≥ 0.750

5.2. Results of Exploratory Factor Analysis (EFA)

Table 3: Results of Exploratory Factor Analysis (EFA)

Factor	KMO Coefficient	Sig	Total Variance Explained	Factor Loading Coefficient
1. Independent Variables	0.894	0.000	73.729	
Attitude				0.765 – 0.848
Subjective Norm				0.758 – 0.855
Perceived Risk				0.795 – 0.895
Perceived Price				0.695 – 0.808
Ethical Perception				0.769 – 0.867
2. Dependent Variable	0.811	0.000	74.164	
Intention to Use				0.791 – 0.923

Regression Analysis Results and Hypothesis Testing

From Table 3, we can see that the R2 value has a very small Sig. value (Sig. = 0.000), indicating that the regression model is appropriate. All five variables contribute to explaining 69.3% of the variance in customers' intention to use. The Tolerance values are quite high, ranging from 0.587 to 0.841, and all VIF values are below 10. This indicates that multicollinearity among the independent variables is very low, aligning with the assumption in this study that the variables are independent of each other.

The results in Table 5 show that four independent variables positively influence the intention to use Netflix movies service among employees with statistical significance at a 95% confidence level in decreasing order of magnitude: Price Perception ($\beta = 0.394$), Attitude ($\beta = 0.124$), Ethical Perception ($\beta = 0.123$), Subjective Norm ($\beta = 0.109$), and Risk Perception ($\beta = -0.093$).

Table 5: Results of Regression Model Analysis

Model	Unstandardized Coefficient		Standardized Coefficient	Significance Level	Multicollinearity Test	
	B	Standard Error	Beta		Tolerance	B
(Constant)	1.235	0.245		0.000		
Attitude	0.124	0.039	0.247	0.002	0.841	1.190
Subjective Norm	0.109	0.038	0.241	0.005	0.716	1.396
Risk Perception	-0.093	0.028	-0.256	0.001	0.795	1.258
Price Perception	0.394	0.041	0.627	0.000	0.587	1.703
Ethical Perception	0.123	0.042	0.246	0.004	0.720	1.389

Dependent variable: Intention to use Netflix movie streaming service; Adjusted R2 = 0.693

From the above analysis, we obtain an equation describing the variation of factors influencing the intention to use the Netflix movie streaming service by employees in Vietnam. All factors are accepted in the regression equation. Standardized regression equation: $Y = 0.247* \text{Attitude} + 0.241* \text{Subjective norm} + (-0.256) * \text{Risk perception} + 0.627* \text{Price perception} + 0.246* \text{Moral obligation}$

According to the standardized regression equation, the factor of Price Perception has the strongest positive impact (0.627) on the intention to use the Netflix movie streaming service. This indicates that users consider the price level as a significant factor in their intention to use the service. Following that, the second most influential factor is Risk Perception, followed by Attitude, Moral Obligation, and finally Subjective Norm.

6. CONCLUSION AND MANAGEMENT IMPLICATIONS

Firstly, price perception has the most significant impact on the intention to use Netflix movies streaming services by employees in Vietnam. This indicates that consumers find the current prices for Netflix movie packages reasonable. However, managers should consider offering additional services and regularly updating the content on the Netflix movies platform. The

streaming platform should update its movie library more frequently with trending and popular movies on the market. The translation team should also improve the quality of subtitles and provide creative advertising tools to attract consumers. Furthermore, service providers should implement promotional programs such as discounts during peak hours, bundled service packages, and special pricing to encourage consumers to use Netflix movies services more frequently.

Secondly, risk perception strongly influences the intention to use Netflix movie streaming services by employees in Vietnam. Managers should make commitments to quality when customers use Netflix movie services. Since this is a technically advanced service, businesses should focus on service quality, high-quality video and audio, to provide the best possible experience for customers when choosing to use the company's online movie streaming services. In addition, consumers are concerned about personal information security and data stored on their personal devices. They believe that even though administrators claim that Netflix movies services are completely secure and cannot be infected with viruses from their websites, consumers still have many concerns. This is inevitable because consumers have had negative experiences in the past that have affected their psychology. Therefore, with such ongoing issues, administrators need to provide solutions to protect consumers, such as ensuring the security of personal information, investing in appropriate budgets, and developing data security policies and customer information through the hiring of professional security companies to advise on mechanisms and security policies for both hardware and software systems. Information protection policies should be communicated to users when using the service, along with commitments to responsibility and mechanisms for collecting, using, and storing personal data. Companies also need to regularly advise and guide users on how to protect themselves.

Thirdly, a positive attitude positively affects the intention to use Netflix movie streaming services by employees in Vietnam. Once consumers have confidence and awareness that using Netflix movie services brings them satisfaction, enjoyment, and sophistication in their way of life, their decision to use the service will increase significantly. This encourages managers to further invest in Netflix movie websites, create beautiful interfaces, easy-to-use features, attractive promotional programs, and a library of frequently updated movies that are currently popular in the market. Additionally, businesses should invest in attractive features that not only provide online movie streaming services but also help users learn. For example, foreign movies should not only have Vietnamese subtitles but also display both English and Vietnamese subtitles simultaneously to help those who want to learn English use online streaming services for entertainment and relaxation while also improving their English skills through movies. Since it is a technically advanced service, businesses need to create a two-way communication channel, a convenient information exchange channel for customers before, during, and after using the service. For example, using social media tools like Facebook and Zalo or creating an information exchange channel with many similarities to customers, regularly having a receiving and responding department, as well as supporting customers when incidents occur during the service usage process.

Fourthly, ethical awareness has a relatively positive impact on the intention to use Netflix movie streaming services by employees in Vietnam. This factor affects the psychology of consumers, as using Netflix movie services provides consumers with a sense of pride and sophistication in their way of life, as well as a high level of awareness in protecting intellectual property rights and copyright. Managers need to strengthen the dissemination of intellectual property laws through the media, intensify marketing efforts, create highly creative advertisements to enhance consumer awareness and habits regarding the ethics of using intellectual property products. Besides, increasing awareness among consumers, especially focusing on educating the younger generation, is crucial. The use of licensed Netflix movie services by consumers also encourages others to participate. They will become bridges and role models for the whole society to follow and consume correctly.

Fifthly, subjective norms have a relatively moderate relationship with the intention to use Netflix movie streaming services by employees in Vietnam. Consumers will mainly rely on the value they receive from the service to decide whether to use it, with less influence from others or social networks. However, this factor should not be overlooked in promoting consumers' intention to use. Regardless of whether it is acknowledged or not, this factor still has some influence on consumers when they weigh whether to use the service or not. In cases where consumers are influenced by various external factors, making them lean towards using the service in the future, it is crucial for businesses and managers to strengthen marketing efforts and focus on consumer psychology regarding enjoyment and ethical considerations. This can improve consumer understanding, usage, and a good experience, which will be word-of-mouth among consumers, and positive experiences will be transmitted from one person to another. Moreover, the government should improve legal documents on the management, provision, and use of broadcasting and television services to thoroughly address the issue of unlicensed online movie streaming services. This can help shape consumer behavior to prevent them from using these services.

In conclusion, this research has found evidence for the important role of factors such as price perception, attitude, ethical awareness, subjective norms, and risk perception in the intention to use Netflix movie streaming services. Furthermore, nearly 60% of consumers in Vietnam have registered to use paid online streaming services, which is a promising sign. This could be the starting point for implementing strategies to promote and advertise to influence consumer psychology in the Vietnam region, or even nationwide. Therefore, marketing strategies for Netflix movie streaming services can focus on consumer groups interested in the service.

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